

CARBIMAZOLE-INDUCED HYPOTHYROIDISM PRESENTING WITH CONVULSIONS: A THERAPEUTIC PARADOX

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Article Received on 05 May 2026,

Article Revised on 25 May 2026,

Article Published on 01 June 2026,

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How To Cite This Article: Aaron Abhishek K.*, Nishad Anjum¹, H.S. Pooja², Dr. Chitrahasini Savanthi, Dr. Namratha Dumthi (2026). Carbimazole-Induced Hypothyroidism Presenting With Convulsions: A Therapeutic Paradox. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 989–995.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Carbimazole is widely used in the treatment of hyperthyroidism. Although effective, excessive suppression of thyroid hormone synthesis may result in iatrogenic hypothyroidism. Neurological manifestations such as seizures are uncommon and may complicate diagnosis. **Case Presentation:** A 53-year-old male with a history of hyperthyroidism on carbimazole therapy for six months presented with syncope and generalized tonic-clonic seizures. Laboratory evaluation revealed elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels (37.483 μ IU/mL) with decreased free T3 and free T4 levels, confirming hypothyroidism. Autoimmune markers including anti-thyroid peroxidase and TSH receptor antibodies were positive. Carbimazole-induced hypothyroidism was diagnosed. The drug was discontinued and levothyroxine therapy was initiated, resulting in clinical improvement.

Conclusion: This case highlights the importance of regular monitoring of thyroid function during antithyroid therapy. Drug-induced hypothyroidism may present with atypical neurological features, leading to diagnostic challenges.

KEYWORDS: Neomercazole, Carbimazole, Hyperthyroidism, Drug-induced thyroid dysfunction.

INTRODUCTION

Hypothyroidism is a common clinical and pathological condition which arises from deficiency of thyroid hormones used in sufficiently by thyroid gland⁽¹⁾. Thyroid glands

produces or secretes thyroid hormones ie triiodothyroni (T3)and thyroxin(T4) which are essential for biological activities like energy, metabolism, growth and regulation. this hormones are controlled by thyroid stimulating hormones TSH. TSH mainly is stimulated by thyroid releasing hormone secreted by hypothalamus. this hormone increase the cellular uptake of iodine from the blood and causes secretion of t3 and t4 hormones in the blood stream. iodine imbalance can cause increased risk of disorders like graves disease, hypothyroidism, Hashimoto thyroiditis.^[2] Its a relatively common endocrine disorder with symptoms of fatigue, muscle cramps, cool intolerance, shortness of breath. physical examination consisting of periorbital oedema, bradycardia, macroglossia, hypoventilation, nonpitting peripheral oedema and cool, dry skin and it can also progress to myxedema crisis which is a major insult to the body like infection, trauma, ischemic events or chronic obstructive disease, exacerbation of congested heart failure.^[1] Hypothyroidism prevalence in general population ranges from 3.8% to 4.6% and the annual incidence of hypothyroidism of 4.1 per 1000 in female and 0.6 per 1000 in male.^[3] The most common cause of hypothyroidism is autoimmune thyroiditis with iron deficiency remain as an important cause other common causes of hypothyroidism include thyroidectomy, radio iodine therapy drugs such as amiodaron, lithium , thioamides, iodine , thalidomide, rifampicin, interferon. drug induced hypothyroidism is an important reversible cause that may occur due to medication affecting thyroid hormone synthesis and metabolism.^[3] Carbimazole is a methimazole derivative it belongs to the class of antithyroid drugs used to treat hyperthyroidism. carbimazole is a prodrug and its active metabolites act by inhibiting the enzyme thyroid peroxidase this inhibition producer the synthesis of thyroid hormone production specifically T3 and T4 levels which helps induce hypothyroidism.^[4,5]

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Carbimazole is a thionamide antithyroid drug widely used in the treatment of hyperthyroidism. It acts as a prodrug that is rapidly converted into methimazole, the pharmacologically active metabolite. Methimazole inhibits thyroid peroxidase, a key enzyme involved in iodide oxidation, iodination of tyrosyl residues in thyroglobulin, and coupling reactions required for the synthesis of triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4). Inhibition of this enzyme results in reduced thyroid hormone production. Excessive suppression of thyroid hormone synthesis can lead to decreased circulating levels of T3 and T4, thereby removing the negative feedback inhibition on the hypothalamic–pituitary axis and causing elevated

thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels. Prolonged or high-dose carbimazole therapy may therefore lead to iatrogenic hypothyroidism, as observed in the present case.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 53-year-old male patient was admitted with complaints of recurrent episodes of sudden onset unconsciousness occurring mainly during the evening hours, associated with convulsions and spontaneous recovery. The patient also reported generalized weakness, decreased sleep, while appetite and bowel and bladder remained normal. The patient had a known history of hyperthyroidism for nearly 6 months and was previously treated with anti-thyroid medication (carbimazole). On admission, the provisional diagnosis considered as syncope with possible cardiovascular or neurological etiology along with hyperthyroidism. The patient was admitted for evaluation and management of suspected cerebrovascular accident (CVA) with convulsions and hyperthyroidism.

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS AND ON EXAMINATION

On general physical examination, the patient was conscious, alert and oriented but complained of weakness. vital signs on admission were recorded as Blood Pressure: 110/80 mmHg, Pulse Rate: 90 beats/min, SpO₂: 97% at room temperature. On Systemic Examination- Cardiovascular System: S1 and S2 heart sounds present with no murmurs. Central Nervous System: Patient conscious and oriented with history suggestive of convulsive episodes. Respiratory System: Bilateral normal vesicular breath sounds.

Abdomen: Soft and non-tender. Final Diagnosis -Syncope with convulsions, Cerebrovascular accident (CVA),Hyperthyroidism.

LABORATORY INVESTIGATIONS

<input type="checkbox"/> Hematology: RBC: $4.68 \times 10^6/\text{mm}^3$ Hematocrit (PCV): 42.3 % Polymorphs: 79 % Lymphocytes: 14 %
<input type="checkbox"/> Electrolytes: Sodium: 140 mEq/L Potassium: 4.4 mEq/L Chloride: 100 mEq/L
<input type="checkbox"/> Renal Function: Serum Creatinine: 1.3 mg/dL
<input type="checkbox"/> Liver Function Tests: ALP: 191 U/L Direct Bilirubin: 0.7 mg/dL Indirect Bilirubin: 0.7 mg/dL
<input type="checkbox"/> Thyroid Profile: TSH: 37.483 $\mu\text{IU}/\text{mL}$ Free T3: 2.09 pg/mL Free T4: 0.16ng/dL Anti-TPO Antibodies: 171.3 IU/mL CK-MB: 0.9 ng/MI ZTSH receptor antibodies: 9.831 U/L

TREATMENT

Carbimazole	10	mg	PO	OD	given	for	3	days
Atorvastatin	40	mg	PO	OD	given	for	4	days
Clopidogrel	75	mg	PO	OD	given	for	4	days
Rivaroxaban	10	mg	PO	OD	given	for	4	days
Aspirin	75	mg	PO	OD	given	for	1	days
Pregabalin	75	mg	PO	OD	given	for	4	days
Pantoprazole	40	mg	IV	OD	given	for	4	days
Ondansetron	4	mg	IV	SOS	given	for	4	days
Levetiracetam	1	mg	IV	STAT	given	for	1	days
Metoprolol	25	mg	PO	OD	given	for	4	days
Diazepam	9	mg	PO	OD	given	for	4	days

Discharge	Medications
Clopidogrel 75 mg	PO OD
Atorvastatin 40 mg	PO OD
Thyronorm 50 mcg	PO OD
Metoprolol 25 mg	PO OD
Levetiracetam 500 mg	PO OD
Pregabalin 75 mg	PO OD
Rivaroxaban 10 mg	PO OD
Pantoprazole 40 mg	PO OD

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates carbimazole-induced hypothyroidism presenting with atypical neurological symptoms. Carbimazole inhibits thyroid peroxidase, reducing T3 and T4 synthesis. Excessive suppression leads to hypothyroidism. The coexistence of anti-TPO and TSH receptor antibodies suggests an autoimmune overlap between Graves' disease and Hashimoto's thyroiditis, which may contribute to fluctuations in thyroid function. Seizures in hypothyroidism are rare and may be attributed to metabolic disturbances or altered cerebral perfusion. In this case, the presentation mimicked a cerebrovascular event, delaying diagnosis. Regular monitoring of thyroid function is essential to avoid overtreatment and associated complications.

CONCLUSION

Carbimazole-induced hypothyroidism is a reversible but important complication of antithyroid therapy. It may present with atypical features such as seizures, posing diagnostic challenges. Early detection and appropriate management are crucial to prevent adverse outcomes.

LEARNING POINTS

- Carbimazole can cause iatrogenic hypothyroidism with prolonged use.
- Hypothyroidism may present with rare neurological symptoms such as seizures.
- Regular thyroid function monitoring is essential during therapy.
- Autoimmune overlap can complicate disease progression.
- Early intervention improves clinical outcomes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank the Department of Pharmacy Practice their support and valuable guidance.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

CVA–Cerebrovascular Accident

TSH – Thyroid Stimulating Hormone

T3 – Triiodothyronine

T4 – Thyroxine

IV – Intravenous

PO – Per Oral

OD – Once Daily

BD – Twice Daily

AST – Aspartate Aminotransferase

ALP – Alkaline Phosphatase

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